

Chemical Examination of the Leaves of *Prunus persica*

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Leaves and fruits of *Prunus persica* (N.O. Rosaceae: Hindi—Aru) are commonly used as anthelmintic¹. Although occurrence of the glucosides of hesperetol² and kaempferol and quercetin in the leaves³ and naringenin⁴ in the bark has been reported, detailed investigation of the leaves has revealed the presence of several interesting chemical constituents.

Air dried powdered leaves (0.8 kg) were percolated with rectified spirit yielding on concentration 11.0 g of a crude material. The filtrate was exhaustively extracted with hexane giving broadly two fractions: (i) hexane soluble, and (ii) alcohol-water soluble. The hexane soluble fraction was combined with the crude material and neutral and acidic components were separated in the usual way.

The neutral component was chromatographed over alumina giving three well defined crystalline substances, m.p. 67–68° (I); 84–86° (II) and 138–39° (III) from the petrol, petrol: benzene 1 : 1 and benzene : chloroform 3 : 1 eluates respectively. Substance I, C₃₁H₆₄*; $\nu_{\frac{KBr}{max}}$ 725, 736, 1465 and 2850 cm⁻¹ was characterised as hentriacontane by m.m.p. and superposable spectra with an authentic sample⁵, while substance II, C₃₁H₆₄O (T.L.C. single spot) having an additional peak at 3451 cm⁻¹ was found to be identical with hentriacontanol⁵; acetate, m.p. 75–76°, C₃₃H₆₆O₂, m.m.p., co-TLC and IR spectra. The Liebermann Burchard positive product III melting at 138–39°; $[\alpha]_D-31^\circ$ † was confirmed as β -sitosterol⁶ through the preparation of its acetate, m.p. 131–32°, C₃₁H₅₂O₂; $[\alpha]_D-36^\circ$, m.m.p., co-TLC and superposable IR spectra.

The acidic portion after usual purification melted at 269–76° and resolved into four spots on TLC of which only one was prominent. After careful repeated chromatography over silica gel and crystallisations a colourless crystalline compound m.p. 286–87°, C₃₀H₄₈O₃ was obtained. This compound responded to Liebermann Burchard and Noller's tests for triterpenoids and its IR spectrum showed peaks at 3452 (hydroxyl group), 1686 (acid carbonyl), 1365 and 1380 (gem-dimethyl group) and 815 (trisubstituted double bond) cm⁻¹. This triterpenic acid formed a monomethyl ester (with ethereal CH₂N₂), m.p. 168–69°, C₃₁H₅₀O₃; $[\alpha]_D+62^\circ$ which could not be easily saponified (8% alcoholic alkali) to the original

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* Satisfactory analyses were obtained.

† Rotations were determined in 1% CHCl₃ solution at 25°.

acid indicating the hindered nature of the carboxyl function⁷. The acid formed a monoacetate (pyridine+Ac₂O), m.p. 285–86°, C₃₂H₅₀O₄; [α]_D+65°. This acetate was converted to methyl ester acetate, m.p. 238–40°, C₃₃H₅₂O₄; [α]_D+80° which failed to undergo SeO₂ oxidation indicating that the acid did not possess an oleanane skeleton⁸. Further the integration of its NMR spectrum confirmed the presence of one double bond (5.30δ), an acetoxy (2.05δ), a carbomethoxy (3.64δ) and seven methyl (0.78–1.11δ) groups⁹ and its mass fragmentation pattern (m/e 262, 249, 203 and 133) indicated the presence of a 12–13 double bond, a C-17 carbomethoxy and an acetoxy group in the molecule¹⁰. All these findings clearly indicated the identity of the acid as ursolic acid¹¹ which was confirmed by m.m.p., co-TLC and superposable IR spectra of the free acid and its methyl ester acetate with the authentic ursolic acid and methyl ursolate acetate.

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